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NAJERAH DADAYAN EZA, MTISAL, MAED (CAR)

Instructor 2

Mindanao State University - Integrated Laboratory School

Marawi City, Lanao Del Sur, Philippines

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Mga Alaala Sa Aming Munting Tahanan

Sa pagsibol ng panahon,
Sa aming munting tahanan,
Binuo ng aming ama,
Samahan naming di malimot.

Parang kailan lang,
Sa loob at labas nito'y,
Laging nakaantabay,
Aming ilaw ng tahanan.

Mga munting bituin,
Saloobing kumikislap.
Sa mga sandaling,
Yakap nyo'y nariyan.

Mga patak ng pagsubok,
Inyong itinuro sa'min,
Na laging magpakatatag,
At manalig sa Maykapal.

Dumaan ang panibugho,
Winasak ang lungsod,
Sa ngayong sapalaran,
Aral nyo'y pinagyaman.